

Predicting Hypotension after Spinal Anaesthesia Induced with 0.5 % Hyperbaric Bupivacaine for Infraumbilical Surgeries using Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index

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Abstract:

Introduction: The study focuses on predicting post-spinal anaesthesia hypotension in patients undergoing various infraumbilical surgeries by assessing the inferior vena cava collapsibility index as a tool to predict post spinal hypotension.

Aim and Objectives: Predicting hypotension before and after spinal anaesthesia induced with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine for infraumbilical surgeries using inferior vena cava collapsibility index and to determine the effect of preloading on changes in the incidence of post spinal hypotension as directed by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index.

Materials & Methods: The study conducted at Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Centre, Tumkur, Karnataka, India, over 24 months was a prospective, longitudinal study using purposive sampling. It focused on patients aged 18-60, ASA Class I & II, undergoing elective infra-umbilical surgeries under spinal anaesthesia. Patients were divided into two groups: one where the Inferior vena cava collapsibility index (CI) was measured before anaesthesia and another where it was not. If IVCCI measurement was >40%, fluid boluses were given. Hemodynamic were monitored intraoperatively, and post-spinal anaesthesia hypotension was managed with fluids and vasopressors. Data analysis employed unpaired t-tests to compare outcomes between the groups.

Results: 166 ASA I and II patients undergoing elective infraumbilical procedures were divided into CI and NCI groups. The CI group underwent assessment of the Inferior Vena Cava (IVC) collapsibility index, with administration of crystalloids (0.9% Normal Saline) until the index was ≤40%. Patients in the NCI group did not undergo IVC collapsibility index measurement and proceeded directly to surgery following standard protocol. The overall incidence of post-spinal hypotension was 41%, notably higher in the NCI group (29%) compared to the CI group (12%). Patients in the CI group received a higher volume of preoperative fluids (587.35±123.92), whereas intraoperative fluid administration was higher in the NCI group (801.81±353.76). These findings indicate that adequate preloading based on the IVC collapsibility index in the CI group contributed to reducing the incidence of post- spinal hypotension to 12% within that cohort.

Conclusion: Assessing post-spinal anaesthesia hypotension using the inferior vena cava collapsibility index before and after administering 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine reduces its occurrence. The group where the inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured received significantly lower perioperative intravenous fluids and vasopressors compared to the group where it was not measured. Preloading fluids guided by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index before spinal anaesthesia induction effectively reduces the incidence of post-spinal hypotension.

Keywords: Hypotension; Inferior vena cava collapsibility index; Infraumbilical surgeries; Spinal anaesthesia.

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Introduction

Spinal anaesthesia is a secure and dependable technique commonly employed in a range of lower abdominal, orthopaedic, and obstetric surgeries. Some of the benefits include quick action, cost efficiency, ease of administration, and a lower occurrence of adverse effects. Hypotension and

bradycardia are the predominant adverse effects of spinal anaesthesia and can result in serious consequences including myocardial infarction, postoperative delirium, and fatality. [1,3] Intraoperative hypotension frequently occurs in patients who have surgery while under spinal

anaesthesia, with an incidence ranging from 8.2% to 64%. Spinal-induced hypotension mostly occurs due to sympathetic blocking, decreased systemic vascular resistance, and diminished venous return. While the exact etiology of this condition is complex and involves several factors, one of the primary causes that may be changed is a lack of fluids, either absolute or relative. This can be addressed by administering a fluid challenge to increase the amount of blood pumped by the heart. [2,3] While fluid administration and/or vasopressor medications are commonly employed to avoid spinal-induced hypotension, it is important to note that these treatments include potential dangers, such as hypervolemia or reactive hypertension.

Administering large quantities of crystalloids during the perioperative period can cause significant adverse effects on multiple organ systems. These effects include reduced left ventricular stroke volume, increased risk of myocardial ischaemia, impaired pulmonary function, prolonged paralytic ileus, decreased tissue oxygenation, and elevated risk of electrolyte imbalances. Furthermore, the administration of constant-rate norepinephrine or phenylephrine infusions has been linked to the development of reactive hypertension, with reported occurrence rates ranging from 4.8% to 7.3% [3].

The volume status is determined based on specific criteria. Predicting post-spinal anaesthesia hypotension can be accomplished using several methods, including pulmonary arterial catheterization, heart rate variability, inferior vena cava collapsibility index, passive leg lift test, or perfusion index. Among these sonographic measurements, the Inferior vena cava collapsibility index appears to be a safe, straightforward, non-invasive, and cost-effective method for predicting volume status. [4,5] The inferior vena cava collapsibility index is utilized as a quantitative metric to evaluate the degree of collapse in the inferior vena cava during inhalation.

The subcostal approach was employed in this study to determine the Inferior vena cava collapsibility index prior to Spinal anaesthesia. This information was then used to guide fluid therapy and compare the occurrence of Post spinal hypotension between the groups in which the Inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured (CI) and the group in which it was not measured (NCI). If the inferior vena cava collapsibility index exceeds 40%, preloading with 0.9% normal saline was done. [4]

Aim and objectives:

The objective of this study was to forecast the occurrence of hypotension before and after the administration of spinal anaesthesia with 0.5%

hyperbaric bupivacaine for infraumbilical surgeries.

This prediction was based on the measurement of the inferior vena cava collapsibility index.

The primary objective was to compare the occurrence of post spinal hypotension between groups where the inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured and groups where it was not measured. The secondary objective was to assess the impact of preloading on the occurrence of post spinal hypotension, based on the inferior vena cava collapsibility index.

Material and Methods

The study was done as a hospital-based prospective, longitudinal study at the Department of Anaesthesiology, Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Centre, located in Tumkur, Karnataka, India. Patients aged 18-60 years, classified as ASA Class I & II, who were undergoing elective infra-umbilical surgeries under spinal anaesthesia, were recruited for the research after obtaining clearance from the institutional ethics committee and informed consent from the patients. Patients between the age of 18-60 years of ASA grade I & II, scheduled for elective infraumbilical surgeries requiring spinal anaesthesia were included in present study.

Patients with pre-diagnosed hypertension, obstructive or restrictive lung diseases or with increased intra-abdominal pressures like ascites, pregnancy, tumours, having BMI > 40 kg/m², or unwilling to give consent were excluded from the study.

Sample size calculation was done by employing Purposive sampling technique & the formula for calculating the sample size is $n = \{Z(1-\alpha) + Z(1 - \beta)\}^2 [p_1(1-p_1) + p_2(1-p_2)] / (p_1 - p_2)^2$ Assuming 18% of the subject with incidence of hypotension in CI group and 38% of the subjects in NCI group, to achieve power of 80% for detecting difference in proportions of 0.2 between two groups, the minimum sample size required was 75 in each group. That was a total sample size of 150, assuming equal group sizes. Considering non-response rate of 10%, the total sample size required was 166.

Methodology:

After a detailed history, thorough clinical examination and routine surgical investigations were done, patients posted for elective infraumbilical surgeries under spinal anaesthesia, were randomly divided as inferior vena cava collapsibility index measured (CI) and non-inferior vena cava collapsibility index measured (NCI) groups before spinal anaesthesia.

Group CI – inferior vena cava collapsibility index was assessed and later followed by spinal anaesthesia.

Group NCI- Spinal anaesthesia was given without assessing inferior vena cava collapsibility index.

In Group CI, Inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured preoperatively in supine position, using curvilinear probe 2-5 Hz, using M – modality at subcoastal view around 2-3 cm from the right atrium in the long axis. IVC maximum measured at maximum end expiration, IVC minimum diameter measured at end inspiration. Inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured using the formula: $IVC (max) - IVC (min) / IVC (max) * 100$

Inferior vena cava collapsibility index more than 40% was considered as fluid responders and I.V bolus fluids with 500 ml crystalloid (0.9% Normal Saline) was infused over 15 mins. Then inferior vena cava collapsibility index measurement was repeated. If inferior vena cava collapsibility index was still > 40 %, another 500 ml crystalloid was infused.

This was done till inferior vena cava collapsibility index was measured < 40%. After noting inferior vena cava collapsibility index, patients were shifted

to OT, connected to monitors and spinal anaesthesia given. In group NCI, spinal anaesthesia was given without inferior vena cava collapsibility index measurement. Under aseptic precautions spinal anaesthesia was given in sitting position, preferably at L3-L4 interspace, using 25 G Quincke's spinal needle. Appropriate dose of 0.5% hyperbaric Inj. Bupivacaine was injected into subarachnoid space after confirming adequate CSF backflow.

In supine position, motor and sensory level assessed. Significant hypotension was considered if fall in systolic blood pressure will be > 25% or MAP < 60 mmHg. Patients excluded were if adequate level of subarachnoid block not attained after SA. In both groups, if hypotension develops, 500 ml bolus crystalloid (0.9% Normal Saline) was given and if hypotension persists, Injection Ephedrine 6 mg bolus was given.

After two doses of Ephedrine, again 500 ml bolus of fluid was rushed and then Injection Ephedrine 6 mg bolus repeated till hypotension was corrected. Intraoperative hemodynamics was monitored. Post spinal anaesthesia hypotension was managed with fluids and vasopressors.

Figure 1: IVCCI index being measured in group ci patients prior to spinal anaesthesia

Parameters measured:

- IVC maximum measured at maximum end expiration

- IVC minimum diameter measured at end inspiration
- Inferior vena cava collapsibility index

- Hemodynamic correction (SBP, DBP and MAP)
- Doses of ephedrine
- The total intraoperative fluid which includes maintenance and bolus fluids
- Total perioperative fluids which include pre-operative and intraoperative fluids

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 18, Chicago, Illinois, USA. Mean \pm standard deviation was used for the continuous variables with normal distribution, whereas median or interquartile range was used for non-normally distributed variables. Numbers or percentage was used for the categorical variables. Unpaired t-test was done for continuous data.

The data on the nominal scale were compared using the Chi-square test. Inferior vena cava collapsibility index association with hypotension within CI group

was analyzed with binary logistic regression analysis and Chi-square test was used to detect statistical significance. Inferior vena cava collapsibility index correlation with total fluids infused within CI group was done with Pearson's correlation. r^2 value was analyzed for correlation. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant with 95% confidence interval. Receiver operating characteristics will be plotted and the cut off values of Inferior vena cava Collapsibility Index will be determined. Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive Predictive Value, Negative Predictive Value and Accuracy will be calculated.

Results

The demographic characteristics of both groups, including the following: age, gender, co morbidities, habits, ASA grades, amount of intrathecal drug, level of subarachnoid block achieved and BMI were found to be similar and comparable ($p > 0.05$). [Table 1]

Table 1: Demographic data

Variables		Group CI (n=83) (%)	Group NCI (n=83) (%)	P- Value
Age (years)	≤ 20	04 (4.8)	04 (4.8)	0.120 (NS)
	21-30	20 (24.1)	12 (14.5)	
	31-40	18 (21.7)	10 (12.0)	
	41-50	10 (12.0)	22 (26.5)	
	51-60	18 (21.7)	22 (26.5)	
	≥ 60	13 (15.7)	13 (15.7)	
Gender	Male	65 (78.3)	56 (67.5)	0.116 (NS)
	Female	18 (21.7)	27 (32.5)	
Co-morbidities	NA	72 (86.7)	65 (78.3)	0.354 (NS)
	Hypothyroidism	01 (1.2)	02 (2.40)	
	DM type 2	10 (12.0)	16 (19.3)	
Habits	NA	47 (56.6)	60 (72.3)	0.212 (NS)
	Alcoholic	10 (12.0)	07 (8.4)	
	Alcoholic & Smoker	06 (7.2)	04 (4.8)	
	Smoker	20 (24.1)	12 (14.5)	
ASA grade	I	39 (47.0)	43 (51.8)	0.535 (NS)
	II	44 (53.0)	40 (48.2)	
Amount of 0.5% Hyperbaric Bupivacaine (cc)		3.424 \pm 0.279 (Mean \pm SD)	3.384 \pm 0.310 (Mean \pm SD)	0.387 (NS)
level of subarachnoid block achieved	T6	03 (3.6)	04 (4.8)	0.732 (NS)
	T8	08 (9.6)	12 (14.5)	
	T10	56 (67.5)	54 (65.1)	
	T12	16 (19.3)	13 (15.7)	
BMI	< 23.0	69 (83.1)	65 (78.3)	0.205 (NS)
	23.0-24.9	14 (16.9)	18 (21.7)	

NS- Non Significant

There was a statistically significant difference between groups, for the mean amount of IV fluids administered prior to surgery and during surgery. In the CI group, vasopressors were administered to 10 patients and hypotension was noted in 73 patients, whereas hypotension was not seen in 73 patients, which was statistically significant. [Table 2]

Table 2: Comparison of intravenous fluids and vasopressors administered

Variables		Group CI (n=83) (Mean ± SD)	Group NCI (n=83) (Mean ± SD)	P- Value
IV fluids amount (ml)	Preoperative	587.35 ± 123.92	224.10 ± 99.80	<0.001 (S)
	Intraoperative	662.65 ± 246.54	801.81 ± 353.76	0.004 (S)
Vasopressors given intraoperatively	No	73 (88.0)	25 (30.1)	<0.001 (S)
	Yes	10 (12.0)	58 (69.9)	

S- Significant

In the CI group, the mean values of the inferior Vena cava maximum, minimum, and collapsibility index were measured.

They are 18.33 ± 1.59 mm, 13.32 ± 1.33 mm, and $26.89 \pm 6.71\%$. Because the NCI group did not measure the inferior Vena Cava maximum, minimum, or collapsibility index, the values

between the two groups cannot be compared. Preoperative and postoperative mean arterial pressures were compared between the two groups using an unpaired t test.

The results showed a statistically significant difference between the groups, with p values of 0.030 and 0.001, respectively. [Table 3]

Table 3: Comparison of IVC CI and MAP

Variables	Group CI (n=83) (Mean ± SD)	Group NCI (n=83) (Mean ± SD)	P- Value
IVC Max (mmHg)	18.33 ± 1.59	00.00 ± 00.00	-
IVC Min (mmHg)	13.32 ± 1.33	00.00 ± 00.00	-
IVC CI (%)	26.89 ± 6.71	00.00 ± 00.00	-
Preoperative MAP (mmHg)	99.77 ± 10.24	96.46 ± 9.20	0.030 (S)
Postoperative MAP (mmHg)	86.23 ± 7.42	82.34 ± 7.55	0.001 (S)

S- Significant

Discussion:

Spinal-induced hypotension mostly occurs due to a reduction in both cardiac output and systemic vascular resistance (SVR). The patient's sensitivity to intraoperative hypotension can be influenced by their preoperative volume status, which might vary based on factors like as co-morbidities, physical condition, preoperative medicines, and fasting. Prior to delivering spinal anaesthesia, it is normal to do prophylactic empiric volume loading in order to mitigate haemodynamic deterioration. However, it has been proven that administering a large amount of fluid before a medical procedure significantly decreases the requirement for vasopressor medications and decreases the occurrence of low blood pressure caused by spinal anaesthesia. Hence, to avoid the occurrence of blind volume loading, there is a growing need to identify predictors of hypotension produced by spinal anaesthesia. In spontaneously breathing people, the measurement of intravascular volume was accomplished by utilizing ultrasonographic assessment of the inferior vena cava (IVC) and the inferior vena cava collapsibility index (IVCCI). This strategy has been demonstrated to be direct, little intrusive, and dependable. [5]

To assess fluid responders, we have established a threshold of an inferior vena cava collapsibility index exceeding 40%. This is derived from the systematic review conducted by Zhang et al. [6] The researchers conducted a study of eight studies including a total of 235 individuals. They

discovered that the threshold for intravascular volume contraction index (IVCCI) ranged from 12% to 40%. In the current study, the total incidence of post-spinal hypotension was 41%, with a statistically significant greater rate seen in the NCI group (29% versus 12%) compared to the CI group. The studies conducted by Ceruti et al. and Ayyanagouda et al. aimed to determine if evaluating the collapsibility index of the inferior vena cava before surgery and administering fluids in individuals with high indices may reduce post-spinal hypotension. [5, 7]

In line with our research, the group that was evaluated based on the non-Inferior vena cava collapsibility index showed a greater occurrence of post-spinal anaesthesia hypotension (PSAH) in both of these studies. The study conducted by Ceruti et al. found that post-spinal hypotension was observed in 27.5% of the group in which the inferior vena cava collapsibility index was evaluated, compared to 42.5% in the group where it was not examined. [7] A research conducted by Ayyanagouda et al. found that post-spinal hypotension occurred in 50% of the group that was assessed and in 20% of the group that was not measured, as determined by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index. [5] The relative risk reduction for our group was 80.25%, whereas the Ceruti et al. and Ayyanagouda et al. groups showed relative risk reductions of 35% and 40%, respectively, for post spinal anaesthesia, as determined by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index. [5, 7]

Preoperative fluid was administered to patients in the present investigation only if their inferior vena cava collapsibility index exceeded 40%; otherwise, it was withheld. Group NCI had a higher occurrence of post-spinal hypotension, which required a larger amount of fluid to be administered quickly. This resulted in a statistically significant increase in intraoperative fluids, including maintenance fluids and additional fluids given in response to post-spinal hypotension, compared to group CI. If the collapsibility index of the inferior vena cava exceeded 40% before to surgery, preloaded fluids were incorporated, into both the overall volume of fluids administered during the perioperative period and the total amount of fluids administered during the surgery. The current research approach had some resemblance to those of Ayyanagouda et al. and Ceruti et al. [5,7]. In all of these studies, the group that had the inferior vena cava collapsibility index assessed received a significantly larger quantity of perioperative fluid compared to the group that did not have the index tested. However, the group with the non-measured index received a greater amount of intraoperative fluid.

The results of our research differed from those of Mačiulienė et al. The researchers examined the potential of utilising the inferior vena cava collapsibility index to forecast post-spinal hypotension at five distinct time points after knee replacement surgery. [8]

Salama and Elkashlan et al. discovered that preoperative ultrasound-guided measurement of the inferior vena cava collapsibility index may also be used to predict post-spinal hypotension. [9] Unlike my inquiry, this study did not provide preoperative fluids based on the inferior vena cava collapsibility index. Instead, it focused on examining postoperative spinal hypotension and its correlation with the preoperatively recorded index.

The group that was guided by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index showed a reduction in the occurrence of hypotension caused by spinal anaesthesia. The measurement of the inferior vena cava collapsibility index can assess a patient's need for fluid preload boluses. The incidence of patients requiring vasopressors to manage hypotension was a reliable indicator of post-spinal hypotension in group CI, with a recorded rate of 12%, much lower than the rate of 29% found in group NCI.

In another study done by Ceruti et al. [7], they compared the administration of fluids guided by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index with the absence of fluid preload infusion before spinal anaesthesia. The group that received fluid administration guided by the inferior vena cava collapsibility index saw a lower occurrence of hypotension. In the study conducted by Ni et al.

[1], a hypothesis was proposed regarding the potential association between increased collapsibility of the inferior vena cava and the occurrence of hypotension during spinal anaesthesia. The sonographic evaluation of the diameters of the inferior vena cava and the computation of the collapsibility index of the inferior vena cava provide a reliable non-invasive tool for directing fluid and vasopressor management during surgery. The utilization of the inferior vena cava collapsibility index-based fluid management strategy should be encouraged for patients receiving surgery with spinal anaesthesia. This is because the postoperative usage of inferior vena cava ultrasonography is both convenient and non-invasive. Prior to administering spinal anaesthesia, it is advisable to measure the collapsibility index of the inferior vena cava. This can help identify individuals who may be susceptible to spinal-induced hypotension, particularly older persons or those who may have low blood volume. [1]

Conclusion

The current research has determined that the occurrence of post-spinal hypotension may be reduced by assessing it using the inferior vena cava collapsibility index before and after administering spinal anaesthesia with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine. In comparison to the group that had their inferior vena cava assessed, the group that did not have their inferior vena cava measured had a considerably larger volume of IV fluids and had a greater utilization of vasopressors throughout the perioperative period. Using the Inferior Vena Cava Collapsibility Index as a guide Prior administration of fluids before initiating spinal anaesthesia reduces the likelihood of experiencing post-spinal hypotension.

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